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Benefits and risks of seafood consumption

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Seafood represents a major part of animal protein consumption in many parts of the world, accounting for 16.7 % of the global population's intake of animal protein and 6.5 % of all protein consumed. Fish proteins can represent a crucial nutritional component in some densely populated countries where the total protein intake levels may be low. Of 136 million tonnes globally utilised as human food, 27 % is consumed fresh and the rest is processed as frozen, salted, dried, smoked, or canned. Being the fastest growing food production system in the world, aquaculture produced 66.6 million tonnes in 2012, adding to a global increase from 9.9 kg per capita fish consumption in the 1960s to 19.2 kg in 2012. This development has been driven by a combination of population growth, rising incomes, and urbanisation and has been facilitated by the strong expansion of fish production and more efficient distribution channels. As seafood is high on the list of foodborne diseases and sources of chemical hazards, safety concerns related to the intake of raw fish are considerable. While scombroid food poisoning can result from eating rotten fish, seafoodborne parasitoses are either caused by ingestion of viable cestodes, trematodes, and nematodes, or can elicit allergic reactions following the sensitisation to the parasite's antigen, as is the case of *Anisakis* spp. In respect of chemicals, bioaccumulation results in a higher concentration of methyl-mercury and arsenic in sea organisms compared to the surrounding environment, while the misuse of veterinary drugs in aquaculture is an important hazard necessary to address during the implementation of the HACCP programme on farms. Although fish and fish products were the most alerted category in 2015 in the EU Rapid Alert System for Food and Feed, the hazards related to contamination or survival of biological hazards during processing are well-defined and can be controlled by applying Good Manufacturing Practice (GMP), Good Hygiene Practice (GHP), and a well-designed HACCP-programme in fishery industry.

KEY WORDS: *Good Hygiene Practice; Good Manufacturing Practice; food poisoning*

Risk assessment of drinking water from public wells

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The aim was to identify microbiological, chemical, and physical hazards in drinking water from public wells, which can have an impact on human health, and to evaluate the results of routine analyses of drinking water safety differently, not considering the national legislative, but rather risk management approach. Drinking water from 20 public wells in South Backa District (SBD) was sampled and analysed during 2016 at the Institute of Public Health of Vojvodina according to the accredited, standardised, and proposed national methodology. The hazards were identified according to international recommendations. Risk assessment was done by applying the semi-quantitative approach, which classifies the likelihood and consequence of an identified hazard in terms of risk as low, medium, high, and very high. Among 218 drinking water samples, only 10 % was in accordance with national regulations. The identified hazards were thermotolerant coliforms (especially *Escherichia coli*), enterococci (genus *Streptococcus*), *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Proteus* species, and nitrates above the proposed level. In two thirds of controlled public wells, the risk was rated as high with an influence on morbidity of sensitive population and in one third as medium, causing the changes in the choice of drinking water sources. The proposed risk assessment methodology enables an easier understanding of information and clearly rates the risk caused by drinking water from public wells. The largest challenge in managing drinking water safety is to systematically prioritise risk assessment in the Republic of Serbia.

KEY WORDS: *coliforms; hazard; human health*

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